

What Motivates Young Indians for Online Shopping? : A Model to Predict Online Purchase Behavior of Gen Y and Gen Z

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Abstract

The e-commerce has transformed the way business is done in India. The Indian e-commerce market is expected to grow to US\$ 200 billion by 2026 from US\$ 38.5 billion as of 2017. Much growth of the industry has been triggered by increasing internet and Smartphone penetration. The ongoing digital transformation in the country is expected to increase India's total internet user base to 829 million by 2021 from 604.21 million as of December 2018 (ibef.org). Customers are moving towards the digital form of purchase rather than physical. The recent growth of e-commerce and the consumer's increasing interest in purchasing over the net have significantly changed the landscape of Indian retail market. In such situation it is become necessary for marketers to study the online purchase behavior of the India customers.

This paper discusses the components of online purchase behavior which are churned out through literature review and then develop a simple and precise model of online purchase intention. This paper conclude that perceived usefulness, perceived self efficacy, trust, attitude and subjective norms has the positive impact on purchase intention which ultimately shapes the actual behavior. Gen Y and Gen Z have almost same shopping behavior.

Keywords: Online Purchase Intention, Gen Y, Gen Z, Structure Equation Model

Introduction

The buying behaviour of consumers has undergone a drastic shift pertaining to increased penetration of internet and various platforms available for purchase through online mediums. In addition, the large Growth in E-commerce continues unabated, with all the business payment options made available by companies. The companies are leveraging the habit of consumers spending maximum time online by integrating it with their marketing strategies. This shift is on account of many contributory factors; including rapid adoption of E-commerce, ease of use, transparent buyer and seller interaction and many such factors.

E-commerce is expanding in the nation. With advancements in quality of payments, online access and calculating on platforms, changed consumer behaviour with a large active internet user base, clients have the ever increasing selection of products at the cheapest prices by several retailers. E-commerce is producing the revolution in the retail industry, and this trend would continue in the years to come. Presently India's net penetration stands at about 35-40percent .It has been found that the e-commerce of India is one of the fastest growing channels for transactions. E-commerce in India is increasing at an yearly rate of 51%, the highest in the world, and is expected to leap from USD 24 billion in 2018 into USD 200 billion in 2026 based on ASSOCHAM-Forrester research newspaper as well Retail Association of India (RAI).

Additionally in an era of global communication and evolution of the web and social websites, when folks make increasingly frequent use of modern technological devices, like smart phones and tablet PCs not just to communicate with their peers, but also to find information regarding the qualities of their favorite goods and/or services (Dabija et al. 2017), merchants will need to stay informed about the newest trends and invent their general business strategies in line with the present behavior of the target groups. Unlike the fully older or elderly, young individuals have a penchant for mass communication, such as pleasurable leisure intervals and effective use of time, tending to concentrate on those tasks that give the greatest benefits and optimize their expertise (Dabija et al. 2018; Dabija 2018). Therefore, online shopping in just an well-developed specialized infrastructure, enabling rapid and easy connectivity (Dabija and Grant 2016) represents an superb premise for e-commerce.

Drawing on generational theory, in which individuals are grouped depending on their year of arrival, the societal events in their lifetime, and the customs, values, tastes, standards, etc., form their own behavior (Inglehart 1977; Egri and Ralsston 2004; Williams and Page 2010), the authors completed exploratory quantitative research on 2 generations--Millennials and Generation Z--at an emerging marketplace. For entrepreneurs, these market segments are getting increasingly more important, as a result of their ever-increasing buying power (Sox et al. 2014), their proclivity for the usage of contemporary means of communicating and their being tech-savvy, with grown up with technology, with the Internet playing a significant role in their life. As they are knowledgeable about online shopping (Nusair et al. 2013), the analysis of their online behavior is of utmost significance. Hence this study tries to find out the predicting variables of online shoppers for gen y and gen z by establishing structural equation model.

Literature Review

Perceived Risk

Perceived risk is a well established theory in consumer behavior (Bauer, 1960). Consumer perceptions of danger have been proven to form purchase conclusions to varying degrees and for that reason influence consumer behavior (Mitchell, 1999). It is apparent that consumers continue to comprehend that utilizing the web for buying is risky (Bourlakis et al., 2008). Those leading to monetary loss, potential violations of privacy and security and product quality declines are often considered the dominant ones (Kim et al., 2008). Cases of financial loss payable are it in the form of payment system failures credit card fraud or even user mistakes which turn controversial. Privacy issues associated with perceived (and often real) lack of management on Internet's collection and use of consumer's private information (Alberto & Montoro, 2007) are quite prevalent.

H1: Perceived risk has the negative impact on the purchase intention

Perceived Usefulness

Perceived usefulness is defined as the level to which consumers believe that the internet site could add value and efficiency to them when performing online shopping (Hu et al., 2009; Lai & Wang,

2012). It translates to the customer's subjective belief he will gain something from the Internet buy (Forsythe et al., 2006). The convenience of shopping in the privacy of home or anywhere and everywhere, the option to save time and money, obtaining a larger selection of products, searching before buying and being in a position to compare offers are some of the perceived advantages that may influence the online purchase goal, behavior and devotion (Hubert et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2017). Perceived usefulness could also be defined by someone's point of view that by making use of a system would improve job performance (Liao et al., 2013).

H2: Perceived Usefulness has the positive impact on the purchase intention

Perceived Self Efficacy

Self-efficacy was described as the subject of understanding of its capacity to control and exert influence within an action or a shift. According to the definition itself, self-efficacy embodies behavioral control in place by TPB. Aside from the selection of applications explored by Bandura himself, even from understanding stress to affecting at-risk behavior among AIDS sufferers, additional investigators have empirically validated the theory in the e-commerce distance (Eastin, 2002; Koufaris, 2002). Igarria and Iivari (1995) clarified that the users with low perception of the self-efficacy in restraining computers tend to avoid them. Consumers in their study (in Finland) displaying higher self efficacy utilized computers more and even sought more management service to facilitate their use. They contended that perceived usefulness alone will not drive the use of an individual against a perception of capacities. Eastin (2002) discovered self-efficacy is the most crucial predictor of online shopping.

H3: Perceived Self efficacy has the positive impact on the purchase intention

Trust

Trust can be described under conditions of addiction and danger. Hope and the consumer experience on the computer medium is very likely to affect his level of confidence. Trust is a significant element in online shopping (Jarvenpaa and Tractinsky, 1999). Trust makes customers making purchasing comfortable sharing info, and behaving on the information, all which can be essential to adoption of internet shopping of retailer. Bianchi and Andrews (2012) pointed out this both confidence favorably influence the mindset of customer towards internet shopping. A trust connection that is favorable could lead to search online.

H4: Trust has the positive impact on the purchase intention

Subjective Norms

Subjective Norms needed a positive impact on Intention to use online shopping. This finding is comparable with several research (Patterson et al., 1997, Sukaran, 2003). These results imply that customers believe that their friends, family members, and media may reinforce engaging and openness in online connections and this belief functions in forming their intention to work with online shopping. It is important to remember that generally, their collectivism culture is reflected by Jordanian consumers and therefore they are heavily influenced by the expectations of individuals around them.

The Majority of the Studies on subjective standard are mediated by purchase intentions before a related finding by Mat and Jamil (2011) proposed that subjective standard doesn't substantially influence actual Buying through the web but have a deep effect on internet Buy intention. The results implied that families, friends and the media only have a minor impact on the actual internet purchasing. Subjective norm was the most influential factors after perceived behavioral control to affect. The buying intention to look online (Orapin, 2009) is hypothesized the recommendations from third parties (subjective standard) significantly impacted the buy intention of the customers.

H5: Subjective Norms has the positive impact on the purchase intention

Attitude

Attitude is one of the two important determinants of voluntary behavior, initially suggested in the TRA (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975) and further extended in TPB (Ajzen, 1991). In these theories, attitude was defined as the results of beliefs held by the subject regarding the results of an action in terms of favorableness or unfavorableness. In any decision-making process, these preceding cognitive beliefs stored in memory are readily available and they influence the decision (Fazio, Ledbetter, and Towles-Schwen, 2000). An online shopping mindset refers in terms of earning purchases to customers' condition. While Rokeach (1967, 1968) discovered that mindset is a group of interrelated predispositions to action organized around a thing or a situation. Social attitudes are assumed to be indicative of past experiences that direct the future behavior (Campbell D, 1963). Consumers' mindset is a factor which has an impact on the customers' purchasing openness. It is so important to realize that attitude formation is preceded by things and change. Therefore, understanding customer attitudes help marketing managers assess the rise of internet commerce and to predict the shopping rate (Delafrouz, Paim, Haron, Sidin, Khatibi, 2009). So as to explore consumers' attitudes, the researcher examined several factors that might influence consumers' attitude towards shopping. Basically, this usually means there isn't any point in the event the types are unlikely to be online, having a fantastic product on the web.

H6: Attitude has the positive impact on the purchase intention

Intention and Actual Behavior

Taylor and Todd (1995) Studies that intention Forecasts behavior (Chen et al., 2015; Zhou et al., 2007). Such assumption Intention is the Asserted that behavioral intention is a fantastic predictor of use behavior for people with experience and familiarity with technology. Cognitive representation of the very best predictor of behavior, and also a person's readiness to perform a given behavior is intention. According to the Theory of Reason Action, the stronger the intention of a person to execute a specific behavior, the greater the particular behavior is going to be done (Ajzen, 1991). Derives from well-established notions and has empirical support (Lin, 2007). Based on Brown (2003), customer with intentions to purchase certain merchandise will exhibit higher actual buying rates than those customers who demonstrate they don't have any intention of buying.

Research Methodology

The main objective of the study was to predict the online purchase behavior through structure equation model so online shoppers are taken as the sample units. 505 online shoppers are finalized as the sample size. Sample units are selected through non probability, Judgmental and referential techniques. Descriptive research design was adopted for this study. Primary data were collected through the structured questionnaire and secondary data were collected from various books, journals, and websites and research projects. Variables namely perceived risk, perceived usefulness and perceived self efficacy, trust, subjective norms attitude, purchase intention and actual behavior are adopted from the Singh and Srivastava (2018). All the items are measured on five point Likert scale.

Analysis

Demographic Profile

Out of 505, 325 respondents are male and remaining respondents are females. 60.3 percent of the respondents are married. 71.1 percent of the respected has the at least graduation degree. 39.3 percent of the respondents are salaried and 31.7 percent of the responds are belonged to business class.

Measurement Model

The constructs were subjected to confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to verify that the manifest variables load upon the proposed constructs and are indeed indicative of these constructs. The combination of CFA and construct validity assessments allows the researcher to evaluate the quality of their measures within a measurement model prior to testing the structural model. Measurement model indicate that there are 8 eight latent variables with the 28 indicators.

Table 1 Convergent Validity and Reliability

Factor	Indicator	Factor Loading	AVE	Cronbach's alpha(α)
Perceived Self Efficacy	pse1	0.8584	0.7653	0.8972
	pse2	0.9295		
	pse3	0.8476		
	pse4	0.8614		
Perceived Usefulness	Puse1	0.8275	0.6741	0.8288
	Puse2	0.6067		
	Puse3	0.9194		
	Puse4	0.8935		
Trust	t1	0.8239	0.6841	0.885
	t2	0.8298		
	t3	0.8593		
	t4	0.7645		
	t5	0.8546		
Subjective Norms	sn1	0.9083	0.8075	0.762
	sn2	0.8888		
Attitude	att1	0.8537	0.7625	0.8961
	att2	0.8846		
	att3	0.8405		
	att4	0.9123		
Purchase Intention	int1	0.8724		0.8081
	int2	0.7285		
	int3	0.9379		
Perceived Risk	pr1	0.6979	0.6895	0.8461
	pr2	0.8381		
	pr3	0.8791		
	pr4	0.8919		
Actual Behavior	ab1	0.9873	0.9748	0.9742
	ab2	0.9873		

Measurement model was run and factor loading was checked. Factor loading was first evaluated for the convergent validity. Factor loading more than 0.7 indicated as the excellent loading where factor loading up to 0.5 also indicate acceptable fit. All the factors have loading more than 0.5 and majority of the factors have loading more than 0.7. Factor loading conclude that all the indicators are convergent in to said latent variables. AVE (Average Variance Extracted) is also evaluated

for the convergent validity. Value of AVE greater than 0.5 is considered as excellent convergent validity. Tables 1 indicate that all the latent variable has the higher than 0.5 value which also again confirm that model possess the excellent convergent validity.

It is important to find out internal constituency of the measurement prior to further analysis. Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of reliability can be used to find out the reliability of the scale. According to Nunnally (1978), Cronbach’s alpha value more than 0.70 indicate good level of internal consistency. Here, reliability coefficients are found to be more than the standard value of 0.70 which provides the good construct reliabilities for the constructed scales.

Table 2 Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Construct	Perceived Risk	Perceived Usefulness	Trust	Subjective Norms	Perceived Self Efficacy	Attitude	Purchase Intention	Actual Behavior
Perceived Risk	0.6895							
Perceived Usefulness	0.4047	0.6741						
Trust	0.3021	0.6277	0.6841					
Subjective Norms	0.6869	0.3992	0.205	0.8075				
Perceived Self Efficacy	0.5988	0.4643	0.3213	0.5093	0.7653			
Attitude	0.4701	0.3254	0.2641	0.2416	0.2113	0.7625		
Purchase Intention	0.549	0.6493	0.6695	0.445	0.6675	0.3796	0.7239	
Actual Behavior	0.4398	0.6547	0.6666	0.3673	0.4409	0.3426	0.6749	0.9748

Figure 1 Overall Path Model

Discriminate validity indicates the how one variable is discriminate from the other variables. Fornell-Larcker Criterion shows inter latent variable correlation and acceptable cut of point of

the highest correlation between variables (Shown Diagonally in the table). Diagonal Value must be greater than the corresponding row and column correlation value. Table 2 indicates that all the correlation values are less than respective diagonal value. Hence Fornell-Larcker Criterion concludes for the excellent level of the discriminate validity for the model.

SRMR (Standardized Root Mean square Residual) is a measure if the mean absolute value of the covariance residual, is used as the indicator of the goodness of fit for the model. A value less than 0.10 or 0.08 are considered as the good fit (Hu and Bentler, 1999). SRMR value for the model is 0.0737 which indicate the good fit for the model.

Path Model

Path model indicate the structure relation between the studied variables. As shown in the figure 2 this study triesto find out the impact of the antecedent of the online shopping on the intention regarding the online shopping which ultimately leads to the actual shopping behavior of the customer.

Perceived risk has the negative impact on the purchase intention with the beta weight of -0.020. Impact of the perceived risk is not founded statistically significant at five percent level of significant. All the other five factors namely perceived usefulness, Trust, Subjective Norms, Perceived Self efficacy and attitude has the positive impact on the purchase intention. Subjective norms have the least impact compare to all other variables with the beta weight 0.054. Perceived Self efficacy and trust has the highest impact on the purchase intention with the beta weight 0.410 and 0.377 respectively. Attitude toward online shopping and perceived usefulness has the moderate but positive impact on the purchase intention. R square of the purchase intention was 0.880 which indicate that 88 percent of the variance in the purchase intention can be explained through six variables namely perceived risk, perceived usefulness, trust, subjective norms, perceived self-efficacy and attitude.

Figure 2 Online shopping behavior of Gen Y

The beta weight of purchase intention to the actual behavior is 0.822 which indicate that purchase intention has the positive and significant impact on the actual online purchase behavior. R square of the actual behavior is 0.675 which indicate that purchase intention explained approximately 67.5 percent of the changes in the actual behavior of online shopper.

Figure 2 indicate the online shopping behavior of Gen Y and Figure 3 indicate the online shopping behavior of the Gen Z. Close comparison of both model indicate that studied six variables predict the online shopping behavior of Gen Z (R Square = 0.907) more accurately compare to Gen Y (R Square = 0.880).

Perceived risk is not founded statistically significant for both the models. Trust, perceived self-efficacy, perceived usefulness, attitude as well as subjective norms determine the intention of Gen Y towards the online shopping. For Gen Y, trust remains the one of the important factor for the online shopping behavior. Higher the trust level hike the positive intention towards online shopping. Apart from the trust level, attitude subjective norm, perceived usefulness and self-efficacy also shape the final intention level of Gen Y.

Figure 3 Shopping Behavior of Zen Z

Where it comes to Gen Z , Subjective norms, attitude and perceived risk become insignificant for shaping their intention towards the online shopping behavior. Perceived self-efficacy means their self-belief regarding the ability for online shopping is out play to other variables. In addition to the perceived self-efficacy, trust also funded significant contributor in the intention creator with the beta weight of 0.377. Influence from intention the actual behavior founded almost same for both models. Beta weight for Gen Y model is 0.816 and for Gen Z model is 0.835.

Conclusion of the Study

This study concludes that perceived usefulness, perceived self efficacy, trust, subjective norms and attitude has the positive impact on the purchase intention. Perceived risk is negatively influence on the purchase intention. Perceived risk is not significantly contributing towards the online purchase intention. Influence level of subjective norms is moderate where other variables have the higher impact on intention. Furthermore this study concludes that actual online purchase can be predicted through the purchase intention. This study also confirm the reliability and validity of the all the scale in current environment.

One of the important objective of the study was to find out the purchasing behavior model for gen Y and gen Z. The study concludes that studied six variables predict the online shopping

behavior of Gen Z (R Square = 0.907) more accurately compare to Gen Y (R Square = 0.880). Trust is emerged as the most contribution variable for online purchase intention for gen Y where for Gen Z, self efficacy founded most impactful variable. Overall this study concludes that online purchase behavior of Gen Y and Gen Z is more or less same.

Implication of the Study

The current study provides a great insight to managers in the context of online shopping. As consumers begin to comprehend the benefits of online shopping and overcome the period of first adoption, it becomes imperative for its players like Amazon and also Flipkart to engage those consumers with outstanding online consumer experience. In regard to perceived danger, online sellers should implement strategies that promise riskless online payment processing along with secure online shopping experience. According to Collier and Bienstock (2006), online vendors should give paramount significance to three facets of order delivery: timeliness of this order, accuracy of the purchase and status of the purchase. Furthermore, privacy and security of their consumer information have to be ensured in order that these problems are the least of consumers' worries. Internet retailers' mass internet retailers such as Amazon and Flipkart, stand to gain from fostering the perceived usefulness for trend products of their platform. New technologies like virtual walls and virtual mirrors may play a significant role in improving the client experience that is retail encouraging boosting perceptions. Virtual mirrors allow shoppers "try on" clothes and accessories virtually prior to making buying decisions. These merchants need to adapt their business models to provide the consumers with an expertise in addition to adopting the technology. This will involve integrating the powerful facets of in-store experience (measurements, touch-and-feel, guided shopping, etc.) with those of online station (comparison shopping, purchasing, shipping, etc.) (Sopadjieva, Dholakia, and Benjamin, 2017). Finally, to guarantee continuing success of the yet-evolving ecosystem that is e-commerce, it is crucial to involve all stakeholders--programmers as well as customers, entrepreneurs, vendors, site managers -- at the product or service development. A customized and personalized shopping experience will be the surface of prospective e-commerce solutions, and vendors need to build service offerings utilizing innovative technologies. Other new customer base, than the towns is spreading throughout grade 2 and tier 3 cities in India by implementing near-real-time and effective advertising and advertising campaigns, and businesses should target this untapped market.

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